

Chitin and chitosan as antitumour agents : A state-of-the-art mini review[†]

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Abstract : Most of the cases, the tumour in human body causes uncontrollable cell growth and result of cancer. As per World Health Organization (WHO), cancer is the second most frequent cause of death due to disease after heart disease and it will be the cause of death for more than 10 million people in 2020. Therefore, one of the main research goals for researchers are to investigate of new antitumour agents. It is important to find new, powerful anticancer agents that may provide a therapeutic and diagnostic solution to speedy recovery from such diseases. Non biological materials such as chitin and chitosan are biopolymers which have exclusive structural possibilities for chemical and mechanical modifications to generate novel properties and functions. These biopolymers have excellent properties that make it suitable for their usage in various biological systems through drug delivery, tissue engineering, biosensing, drug formulation etc. and due to their unique biodegradability, biocompatibility and non-toxicity properties, they are excellent candidates for cancer cure or its diagnosis. This mini review highlights the numerous methodologies employed by the use of chitin and chitosan as an antitumour agent to fight against various types of cancer causing tumours and to provide a state-of-the-art overview in chitin chemistry.

Keywords : Chitin, chitosan, derivatives, antitumour.

Introduction

Formation of tumour in human body is an unusual phenomenon. At the same time all tumours are not dangerous but many of the cases it may be true. Once tumours are cluster of anomalous cells that form bulges or indefinite growth, it is called malignant, serious and cancerous. Immediate attention needed looking into health care concerns. Hence, tumour is synonymous to cancer. The substance which one is used to prevent or inhibit the formation or growth of tumours is called antitumour. Cancer therapy is still one of the major issue where medicines and research have to be amended for higher efficiency and lessened the side effects. Antitumour activities is mainly performed by alkylating agents, antimetabolites, biopolymers, polymers, anthracyclines and terpenoides and those are delivered by the route of intravenous system of human body^{1,2}. According to WHO, cancer tumor is the major public health concerns in the world and every year, the death rate due to cancer is enhancing which is an alarm-

ing situation. Enhanced understanding of the mechanism of antitumour properties indicates that these might occur through straight mechanisms like introduction of apoptosis and inhibition of tumor cell invasion and adhesion, inhibition of angiogenesis by indirect mechanisms³. Though, many antitumour agents don't have the inherent specificity for malignant tumorous cells, so they also harm other rapid-growing cells. Various types of chemotherapy has proven to be effectual and used world-wide either alone or coalesced with other treatments which is used as a conventional cure of cancer⁴⁻⁷.

Although, this treatment can prolong the survival of the tumor patients but this therapy is also having various side effects like immune suppression, neurotoxicity and myelodominance which can also alter the quality of the life of the patients. As per nature of tumour, it is of various types. Different tumours grow and behave in a different manner, depending upon on whether they are non-cancerous (benign) or cancerous (malignant). Precancer-

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

ous conditions have the potential to develop into cancer. Two main classifications of tumours are benign tumours and malignant tumours.

Benign tumours are usually slow-growing extensive masses that condense rather than invading the surrounding tissue. These tumours are non-cancerous. They hardly cause any critical problems or life-threatening disease unless they occur in any of the essential organ or press on nearby tissues. Benign tumours tend to grow slowly and stay at only one place, not reproducing into other areas of the body. This tumour doesn't usually recur once it is removed by surgery. They usually stay non-cancerous, except in very rare cases.

Whereas, malignant tumours are cancerous. Cancer can start in any one of the millions of cells in the body. These cancerous cells have a larger nucleus. The part of the cell that holds the chromosomes, which contain DNA (genetic information) that looks different from a normal cell's nucleus, and cancer cells behave, grow and function quite differently from normal cells. They grow in an uncontrolled and in abnormal manner and can grow invade immediate tissues, blood vessels or normal cells. This tumour can intervene within the body metabolic activities and causes death. Cancer cells can break off and spread to distant locations in the body. Cancer that spreads from its native location (the primary tumour) to a new location of the body is called metastatic cancer. Malignant tumours can also come back (recur) after they are removed. Besides these two major categories, there are also different types of cancerous tumours (Fig. 1).

From above description, it is understood that due to variation of tumour types the treatment of tumours also needed varieties of medical techniques and medication methods. However, the use of antitumour agents is an old age technique and it is ever-shining treatment procedure. Some of biologically active and non-biological antitumour agents are enumerated below :

Biologically active antitumour agents : The continued development of novel and improved chemopreventive and chemotherapeutic agents continues the prevention and treatment of cancer. From ancient ages the use of natural products from plant, animal, and marine source-like taxol, betulinic acid, camptothecin, resveratrol, podophyllotoxin, curcumin, peroxy compounds, Epothilones and many more have afforded a rich source of anticancer agents with diverse chemical structures and bioactivities⁸⁻¹³.

Non-biological antitumour agents : Non-biological agents include the use of naphthalimide-based antitumor agents¹⁴, perylenebisimide¹⁵, platinum and palladium polyamine complexes¹⁶, non-natural hydroxylated and prenylated xanthenes¹⁷, non-platinum-based halogenated molecules (called femto medicine drug (FMD) compounds)¹⁸ as potent antitumor agents for effective treatment of cancers. Besides these, various kinds of polysaccharides and so many others whose list is unlimited are considered as potential lead candidates for present and future development of novel potent broad-spectrum antitumor agents.

Apart from all techniques/methods polysaccharide based antitumour agents such as chitin and chitosan based various derivatives, matrices are effectively used by many researchers. There are so many reports in literature about the importance of using chitin and chitosan to achieve antitumour effects. It is therefore needed a complete understanding on the property of chitin and chitosan that gives its antitumour agents.

Chitin and chitosan

Structure : Chitin consists 6–8% nitrogen and chitosan contains 8–9.5% nitrogen. In chitosan, between 60 to 80% of the acetyl groups existed in chitin are eliminated¹⁹. The structure of chitin is a biopolymer of *N*-acetyl-D-glucosamine (NAG) allied by beta-glycosidic bonding. The major derivatives of chitin includes polysaccharides, oligosaccharides and monosaccharides which includes vari-

Fig. 1. Types of tumours.

ous therapeutic functions such as immunomodulation^{20,21}, hemostatic²², osteoarthritis cure²³, wound healing, tissue engineering, quantum dots, drug delivery and for regenerative medicines^{24–28}.

Chitin exists majorly in three distinctive polymorphic forms (α , β and γ). These appearances may differ in their padding, arrangements and polarities of contiguous chains in consecutive sheets; in the β -form, all are organized in a parallel manner, which is not case of α -chitin^{29–31}. The molecular arrangement of both α -chitin and β -chitin is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Molecular arrangement and hydrogen bonding in (a) α -chitin, (b) β -chitin.

One of the most unique property of chitin is its proficiency to be molded into various forms like fibers, microspheres, nanoparticles, hydrogels, beads and membranes³². The source of chitin influences its crystallinity, purity, polymer chain assembly, and can enhance its characteristics³³.

Properties of chitin and chitosan : Chitin and its derivatives are highly basic polysaccharides whereas all the biopolymers like alginate, gelatin, pectin, cellulose are acidic in nature.

Physiochemical properties : The main properties of chitin involves solubility in various solvents, solution viscosity, polyelectrolyte behaviour, polyoxysalt preparation, capability to form films, beads, carbon quantum nano dots, hydrogels etc., metal chelations, optical and structural properties^{34–36}. The molecular weight of chitin³⁷ average in the range from 1×10^6 to 2.5×10^6 Dalton but the deacetylation of chitin to chitosan decline the molecular weight to 1×10^5 to 5×10^5 . Its degree of polymerization (DP) ranging between 2000 to 4000. Hydrolysis of

chitin with concentrated acids under extreme situations generates pure amino sugar D-glucosamine moderately. The degree of deacetylation range from 5–15% and 70–95% in chitin and chitosan respectively, the higher degree of acetylation (DA) of chitin the lower solubility in popular solvents³⁸.

Biological properties : They are biodegradable in nature, nontoxic and eco-friendly biopolymers. Chitin is perfectly biocompatible as they have no antigenic characteristics so they are compatible not only with animal but also with plant tissues. It can easily bind to mammalian as well

as microbial cells. Chitin is bacteriostatic, antitumour, hemostatic, immunologic, analgesic, anti-ulcer, anticoliac-diseases, anti-inflammatory, anticoagulant, antibacterial, antifungal, spermicidal, anti-thrombogenic, antiviral and lot more other biological properties^{39–42}. It also has free radical scavenging properties.

Chitin and chitosan as antitumour agents

Chitin and its derivatives owns exceptional characteritic for its use in not only in pharmaceutical applications but also as anticancer agents in various forms like drug formulation, derivatives, nanocarriers for targeted drug delivery systems to fight against various types of tumours⁴³.

Chitin and chitosan itself has excellent antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory features and its inhibitory outcome depends upon its concentration and molecular weight⁴⁴. The antitumour activity of chitin and chitosan results from a simple alteration in its chemical structure, low molecular weight, water solubility and majorly the effect of degree of deacetylation⁴⁵. Fig. 3 shows some activities of chitin/chitosan as antitumour agent.

Fig. 3. Some antitumour activities of chitin/chitosan.

To reduce chemotherapeutic severe side effects, while reducing host resistance to cancer and infections chitin and chitosan and its derivatives play significantly as a therapeutic agent towards anticancer activity. Some work of various research groups for antitumour activity are listed in Table 1.

Besides these, there have been several reviews focussed on chitin/chitosan and its derivatives towards antitumour activity in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* models⁵⁴.

Chitosan and chitin are also utilized as drug carriers to provide anticancer and antitumor chemotherapy which can improve drug absorption, stabilize drug components to

Table 1. Chitin and chitosan and their derivative as therapeutic agents for antitumour activity

Chitin and chitosan and their derivative as therapeutic agents	Antitumour therapeutic activity	References
6-O-Sulfated chitin	Lung tumor colonization inhibition which inhibited the capture of B16B16 cells in lungs after injection with radiolabelled tumorous cells.	46
6-O-Sulfated carboxymethylated chitin (SCM-chitin)	Sarcoma 180 solid tumours in BALB/C mice as well as in MM-46 solid tumours implanted in C3H/HC mice.	47
N-Acetyl chitosan oligomer, mainly the hexane and heptamer	These results analysed that the effect was not by direct cytodial action on the tumorous cells. Hexameric chitosan oligomer had growth-inhibitory effect against Meth-A solid tumour transplanted into BALB/C mice.	47
LMWC was developed by enzymatic hydrolysis using cellulose	Investigated the inhibition of growth of sarcoma 180 tumour cells in mice.	48
Differently charged chitosan oligosaccharides (COS) derivatives using four cancer cell lines : HeLa, Hep3B, SW480 and AGS	Suggested that highly charged COS derivatives could considerably reduce tumour cell viability, regardless of their positive or negative charge.	49
Chitosan and chitin, carboxymethyl-chitosan (CM-chitosan) and carboxymethyl-chitin (CM-chitin)	Their antioxidative and matrix metalloproteinase-2 and -9 inhibitory effects were investigated in HT1080 human fibrosarcomacells. The research suggests CM-chitosan and CM-chitin as potent antioxidants and MMP inhibitor via alleviations of radical-induced oxidative damage.	50
Various molecular weights such as 21, 46 and 120 kDa chitosans by enzymatic hydrolysis	Antitumor activity in sarcoma 180-bearing mice was examined.	51
Copper complexes of chitosan	At the ratio of 0.11 mol copper per one chitosan residue, the complex exhibited a higher antitumor activity and less toxicity. The complex inhibited tumor cell proliferation by arresting the cell cycle progression at the S phase in 293 cells.	52
Conjugating chitosan or chitosan aminooligosaccharide to 5-fluorouracil (5FU)	In order to provide a macromolecular system with strong antitumor activity and reduced side effects.	53
Chitosan-5FU and COS-5FU conjugates	Showed amazing growth-inhibitory effects on Met-A fibrosarcoma and MH-134Y hepatoma. Both conjugates revealed no acute toxicity, even in high-dosages.	

increase drug targeting, and enhance drug release. Safari *et al.*⁵⁵ reported *N,N*-diethyl *N*-methyl chitosan (DEMC) for gene delivery to human pancreatic cancer cells for biological evaluation and mathematical modeling, both results revealed that after DEMC transfection, cancer cell fluorescence intensity and size were altered. There have many reports on chitin/chitosan and its derivatives as bulk carrier for antitumour drug delivery/gene therapy systems.

Besides these, there has been colossal number of researches to explain chitin/chitosan based nanocarriers as antitumour agents as they have the excellent properties of entrapping any kind of drug for target specific (trigger) delivery. Thus, trigger responsiveness polymeric nanocarriers at a tumor site may be attained by passive and active targeting due to anticancer efficiency of such systems by modulating the release of the drug according to the tumour environment.

Yoon *et al.*⁵⁶ synthesized glycol chitosan (GC) nanoparticles which behave as an efficient nanocarriers that can beneficially entrap or adsorb both chemotherapy drug (Doxorubicin, DOX) and si-RNA to attain maximum efficacy. DOX, DOX-encapsulated nanoparticles (CNPs) or Bcl-2 si-RNA-encapsulated CNPs were examined and their physiochemical features which includes size, surface characteristics and pH sensitive behavior were studied, regardless of the distinctive physical features of DOX and Bcl-2 si-RNA, the researcher claim that glycol chitosan based nanocarrier applied to two different types of drugs results in similar *in vivo* bio distribution and chemical kinetics, embellishing treatment in a dose-dependent behavior. In another relevant study, Kim *et al.*⁵⁷ modified glycol chitosan with hydrophobic 5 β -cholic acid and the drug cisplatin was entrapped into the prepared nanoparticles (300–500 nm) using dialysis technique for brain tumour. This research revealed that nanoparticles were fruitfully accrued onto the tumour tissues of tumour-bearing mice due to its prolonged circulation and EPR effect.

The author's laboratory has also developed dibutyl chitin nanocarrier for targeted drug delivery where 5-Fu was entrapped into the carrier and results like cytotoxicity, antibacterial test, swelling behavior reveals that the prepared nanocarrier shows potential to be used as a drug carrier and also for other biomedical applications. Fig. 4 shows the cellular internalization on A549 cells using confocal microscopy⁵⁸.

Fig. 4. Cellular localization on A549 cells after a 6 h incubation period by confocal microscopy of (a) DBC and (b) DBC-Fu nanoparticles⁵⁸.

Recently, Yongling *et al.*⁵⁹ prepared chitosan based carboxymethyl- β -cyclodextrin polymer which was altered by Fe₃O₄ magnetic nanoparticles for delivery of anticancer drug 5-fluorouracil. The results claimed that the quantity of cross linker and time played a vital role in analyzing the morphological characteristics of the prepared hybrid nanocarriers. Therefore, chitosan based antitumour agents as nanocarrier for drug delivery plays a vital role in the treatment of various diseases. Table 2 shows various research outcome to defining and enhancing the antitumour activities of chitin/chitosan and its derivatives as carrier.

In addition, multifunctional entities can be created through decoration with specific molecules such as proteins, peptides, drugs, antibodies, biomimetic ligands, and other ligands. The dawn era of nanotechnology has given a new impetus towards the design and development of biopolymer-based nanocarriers which can undoubtedly alter the shape of human life.

Further, chitin and chitosan for antitumour diagnostics point of views will also play very important role in near future. Biosensing, bioimaging, biolabelling will work as pathway to diagnostics for clinical testing for tumour affected patients.

Conclusion and future perspective

In conclusion, the main focus was to study about topical improved modalities for tumour based on chitin/chitosan and its derivatives. Here, an attempt has been made to enhance the understanding of the various features of chitin and chitosan and its derivatives by describing various researchers outcome and thus to prove that all biopolymers consist of good antitumour activity in terms of therapeutic and drug carrier approach. Further, due to the many biological properties of those polymers, a lot of work can be

Table 2. Chitin/chitosan and their derivatives as carrier for antitumour activity

Chitin/chitosan and their derivatives as carrier	Drug	Entrapment Efficiency (EE)	Method adopted	Type of tumour	References
Chitosan-PEG	Anisamide	75–87	Emulsion	Lung cancer	60
Glycol chitosan	Paclitaxel	90–97	Dialysis	Brain tumour	61
Multifunctional chitosan	Curcumin	69	Emulsion	Cancer	62
Biotinylated chitosan	Bufalin	80	Solvent evaporation and emulsification	Breast tumour	63
			cross-linking		
N,O-Carboxymethyl chitosan	5-Fluorouracil	65	Ionic gelation	Breast cancer	64
Amorphous chitin	Paclitaxel	55	Ionic cross linking	Colon cancer	65
Low molecular weight chitosan	Docetaxel	65	Chemical conjugation	Lung cancer and brain tumour	66
Carboxymethyl chitin	5-Fluorouracil	78.3	Cross-linking	Cancer	67
Glycol chitin	Doxorubicin	–	Cross-linking	Cancer	68

done in the field of medical diagnosis for clinical testing for tumour affected patients. Last but not least, it may be the prospect that chitin/chitosan can really help to revolutionize or to improve existing antitumour agents in various forms like tissue engineering, drug formulation, biosensing (a pathway to diagnostics) for sustaining long life of healthy and recovered human cells.

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References

- X. Yong, Z. N. Jin, C. Jun, D. Bin, S. L. Dong and L. Jin, *J. Clin. Rehabil. Tissue. Eng. Res.*, 2008, **12**, 4579.
- L. F. Qi, Z. R. Xu, Y. Li, X. Jiang and X. Y. Han, *World J. Gastroenterol.*, 2008, **11**, 5136.
- G. Morgana and A. Lipton, "Seminars in Oncology", 2010, pp. S30-S40.
- P. K. Dutta, *Popular Plastics and Packaging*, 1998, **47**, 81.
- D. Elias, F. Blot, A. El Otmány, S. Antoun, P. Lasser, V. Boige, P. Rougier and M. Ducreux, *Cancer*, 2001, **92**, 71.
- A. G. Portilla, P. H. Sugarbaker and D. Chang, *World J. Surg.*, 1999, **23**, 23.
- P. H. Sugarbaker and K. A. Jablonski, *Ann. Surg.*, 1995, **221**, 124.
- E. H. Liu, L. W. Qi, Q. Wu, Y. B. Peng and P. Li, *Mini. Rev. Med. Chem.*, 2009, **9**, 1547.
- T. L. Simmons, E. Andrianasolo, K. McPhail, P. Flatt and W. H. Gerwick, *Mol. Cancer Ther.*, 2005, **4**, 333.
- A. G. Ravelo, A. E. Braun, H. C. Orellana, E. P. Sacau and D. M. Siverio, *Curr. Top. Med. Chem.*, 2004, **4**, 241.
- V. M. Dembitsky, T. A. Glorizova and V. V. Poroikov, *Mini. Rev. Med. Chem.*, 2007, **7**, 571.
- P. H. Pfisterer, G. Wolber, T. Efferth, J. M. Rollinger and H. Stuppner, *Curr. Pharm. Des.*, 2010, **16**, 1718.
- K. H. Altmann and K. Memmert, *Prog. Drug Res.*, 2008, **66**, 275.
- Z. Chen, X. Liang, H. Zhang, H. Xie, J. Liu, Y. Xu, W. Zhu, Y. Wang, X. Wang, S. Tan, D. Kuang and X. Qian, *J. Med. Chem.*, 2010, **53**, 2589.
- Z. Xu, W. Cheng, K. Guo, J. Yu, J. Shen, J. Tang, W. Yang and M. Yin, *ACS Applied Materials & Interfaces*, 2015, **7**, 9784.
- M. P. M. Marques, *ISRN Spectroscopy*, 2013, Article ID 287353, 29.
- X. Zhang, X. Li, S. Ye, Y. Zhang, L. Tao, Y. Gao, Y. D. Gong, M. Xi, H. Meng, M. Zhang, W. Gao, X. Xu, Q. Guo and Q. You, *Med. Chem.*, 2012, **8**, 1012.
- Q. B. Lu, Q. R. Zhang, N. Ou, C. R. Wang and J. Warrington, *E Bio Medicine*, 2015, **2**, 544.
- J. Flash, P. E. Pilet and P. Jolles, *Experientia*, 1992, **48**, 701.
- T. Jain, H. Kumar and P. K. Dutta, "Chitin and Chitosan for Regenerative Medicine", Springer Publications, 2016, pp. 279-299.
- Y. Shibata, I. Honda, J. O. Justice, M. R. Van Scott, R. M. Nakamura and Q. N. Myrvik, *Infect. Immun.*, 2001, **69**, 6123.
- K. Suzuki, T. Mikami, Y. Okawa, A. Tokoro, S. Suzuki and M. Suzuki, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1998, **151**, 403.

23. P. Creamer, *Curr. Opin. Rheumatol.*, 2000, **12**, 450.
24. H. Kumar, R. Srivastava and P. K. Dutta, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2013, **97**, 327.
25. D. Archana, B. K. Singh, J. Dutta and P. K. Dutta, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2015, **73**, 49.
26. C. R. Shen, J. H. Juang, Z. T. Tsai, S. T. Wu, F. Y. Tsai, J. J. Wang, C. L. Liu and T. C. Yen, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2011, **84**, 781.
27. D. Archana, B. K. Singh, J. Dutta and P. K. Dutta, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2013, **95**, 530.
28. T. Jain and P. K. Dutta, *Asian Chitin J.*, 2012, **7**, 13.
29. P. K. Dutta, S. Tripathi, G. K. Mehrotra and J. Dutta, *Food Chem.*, 2009, **114**, 1173.
30. R. Jayakumar, M. Prabakaran, P. T. Sudheesh Kumar, S. V. Nair and H. Tamura, *Biotechnol. Adv.*, 2011, **29**, 322.
31. J. Singh and P. K. Dutta, *Int. J. Polym. Mater.*, 2010, **59**, 793.
32. P. K. Dutta, P. Viswanathan, L. Mimrot and M. N. V. R. Kumar, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 2002, **14**, 351.
33. P. K. Dutta, M. K. Khatua, J. Dutta and R. Prasad, *Int. J. Chem. Sci.*, 2003, **1**, 93.
34. R. A. A. Muzzarelli, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2011, **83**, 1433.
35. J. Singh, S. Kumar and P. K. Dutta, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 2009, **26**, 167.
36. P. K. Dutta, J. Dutta, M. C. Chattopadhyaya and V. S. Tripathi, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 2004, **21**, 321.
37. H. K. No, S. P. Meyers, W. Prinyawiwatkul and Z. Xu, *J. Food Sci.*, 2007, **5**, 87.
38. A. Semwal, B. K. Singh, D. Archana, A. Verma and P. K. Dutta, *J. Polym. Mater.*, 2012, **29**, 1.
39. T. Jain, S. Kumar and P. K. Dutta, *J. Mol. Genet. Med.*, 2015, **9**, 1747.
40. H. Nagahama, N. Nwe, R. Jayakumar, S. Koiwa, T. Furuike and H. Tamura, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2008, **73**, 295.
41. P. K. Dutta, J. Dutta and V. S. Tripathi, *J. Sci. Ind. Res. India*, 2004, **63**, 20.
42. K. Rinki, P. K. Dutta, A. J. Hunt, D. J. Macquarrie and J. H. Clark, *Int. J. Polym. Mater.*, 2011, **60**, 988.
43. J. Vinová and E. Vavíková, *Curr. Pharm. Design.*, 2008, **14**, 1311.
44. L. Y. Zheng and J. F. Zhu, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2003, **54**, 527.
45. C. Qin, Y. Du, L. Xiao, Z. Li and X. Gao, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2002, **31**, 111.
46. J. Murata, I. Saiki, K. Matsuno, S. Tokura and I. Azumo, *Jpn. J. Cancer Res.*, 1990, **81**, 506.
47. K. Suzuki, T. Mikami, Y. Okawa, A. Tokoro, S. Suzuki and M. Suzuki, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 1986, **151**, 403.
48. C. Qin, Y. Du, L. Xiao, Z. Li and X. Gao, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2002, **31**, 111.
49. M. Z. Karagozlu, J. A. Kim, F. Karadeniz, C. S. Kong and S. K. Kim, *Process Biochem.*, 2010, **45**, 1523.
50. C. K. Konga, J. A. Kimb, B. Ahnb, H. G. Byunc and S. K. Kim, *Process Biochem.*, 2010, **45**, 179.
51. Y. Maeda. and Y. Kimura, *J. Nutr.*, 2004, **134**, 945.
52. Y. Zheng, Y. Yi, Y. Qi, Y. Wang, W. Zhang and M. Du, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2006, **16**, 4127.
53. Y. Ohya, T. Takei and T. Ouchi, *J. Bioact. Compat. Polym.*, 1992, **7**, 242.
54. R. C. Fai Cheung, T. B. Ng, J. H. Wong and W. E. Chan, *Mar. Drugs*, 2015, **13**, 5156.
55. S. Safari, M. H. Zarrintan, M. Soleimani, F. A. Dorkoosh, H. Akbari, B. Larijani and M. Rafiee Tehrani, *Advanced Pharmaceutical Bulletin*, 2012, **2**, 7.
56. Y. Hong, S. Sejin, J. So, G. Dong, J. You and Y. Young, *Scientific Reports*, 2014, **4**, 6878.
57. J. H. Kim, Y. S. Kim and K. Park, *J. Control. Rel.*, 2008, **127**, 41.
58. T. Jain, S. Kumar and P. K. Dutta, *Int. J. Biol. Macromol.*, 2016, **82**, 1011.
59. D. Yongling, Z. S. Shirley, S. Huadong, S. Kangning, and L. Futian, *Mater SciEng*, 2015, **48**, 484.
60. N. K. Garg, P. Dwivedi, C. Campbell and R. K. Tyagi, *Eur. J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2012, **47**, 1006.
61. J. H. Kim, Y. S. Kim, S. Kim and J. H. Park, *J. Control. Rel.*, 2006, **111**, 228.
62. Z. Chen, L. Zhang, Y. Song, J. He, L. Wu, C. Zhao, Y. Xiao, W. Li, B. Cai, H. Cheng and W. Li, *Biomaterials*, 2015, **52**, 240.
63. X. Tian, H. Yin, S. Zhang, Y. Luo, K. Xu, P. Ma, C. Sui, F. Meng, Y. Liu, Y. Jiang and J. Fang, *Eur. J. Pharm. Biopharm.*, 2014, **3**, 445.
64. A. Anitha, K. P. Chennazhi, S. V. Nair and R. Jayakumar, *J. Biomedical Nanotechnology*, 2012, **8**, 29.
65. K. T. Smitha, A. Anitha, T. Furuike, H. Tamura, Shantikumar V. Nair and R. Jayakumar, *Colloids and Surfaces B : Biointerfaces*, 2013, **103**, 245.
66. E. Lee, H. Kim, I. H. Lee and S. Jon, *J. Control Release*, 2009, **140**, 79.
67. A. Dev, J. C. Mohan, V. Sreeja, H. Tamura, G. R. Patzke, F. Hussain, S. Weyeneth, S. V. Nair and R. Jayakumar, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2010, **79**, 1073.
68. Z. Li, S. Cho, I. C. Kwon, M. M. Janát-Amsbury and K. M. Huh, *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 2013, **92**, 2267.

